

Speculation on Bohemian Mechanics and The Continuity Equation

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Quantum mechanics is largely based on a wavefunction, which we consider to be a probability. The theory is, however, not solely probabilistic because if an interaction does not occur, $x=vt$ holds as does the classical notion of impulse hit and kinetic energy = $pp/2m$ (nonrelativistic case). The probability $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ describes probabilistic interactions in time and space (we argue) and so one does not think of x and t as in $x=vt$. As a result, there is a probability for a quantum particle to interact with both slits of a two slit apparatus if they are about \hbar/p apart.

This leads us to the notion that $W^*(x)W(x)$ ($W(x)=\text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)=\text{wavefunction}$) is not spatial density, but rather an interaction profile. A particle can still exist at $W(x)=0$ points, it just has very little to no probability of interacting at these points on average, with the average considering both $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ in a bound case scenario. Given that $E=\text{kinetic energy} = pp/2m$ (nonrelativistic case only) and $W^*(x)W(x)$ not= spatial density, we suggest that one must be careful with interpreting $d/dt \text{ partial } W^*(x)W(x) = \text{constant grad dot Im } (W^* (-i\hbar/dx) W)$ (from (1)) as a continuity equation which represents hydrodynamic motion. We suggest that the quantum features are governed by $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ and that any derivatives d/dx and d/dt are related to changes in phase and not hydrodynamic flow (in a classical sense). We note that for a free particle $d/dt \text{ partial density} = 0 = \text{constant grad dot Im } (W^* (-i\hbar/dx) W)$. The same zero equation holds for a bound state (even though there is physical motion to the right and then left), but if one creates a superposition of bound states (which is a probability statement), then the same equation is not 0. We note that for a classical bound state there exists a $v_{rms}(x)$, but this is an average quantity. It does not show any resolution pattern which is represented by $W(x)$ and so one must be careful when interpreting it, we argue.

Quantum Mechanics and Classical Mechanics

Classical mechanics tracks the motion of particles in x,t , e.g.

$x=vt$ ((1)) for a free particle.

Energy, mass and interactions occur at the center-of-mass point. In such a case, it makes perfect sense to write a continuity equation

$$d/dt \text{ partial density}(x,t) = \text{grad dot } (\text{density}(x,t) v(x,t)) \quad ((2))$$

where $v(x,t)$ is a velocity field and one has many particles.

We have suggested in previous notes that

$$\exp(-iEt+ipx) \quad ((3))$$

is a complex probability which describes probabilistic interactions in time and space. Even if $x=vt$, that does not mean that interactions occur at the x and t of the center-of-mass point in this equation. They can occur with probabilities at different times and spatial points. Thus one may have probabilistic interaction with both slits of a 2-slit apparatus if they are about \hbar/p apart.

It is possible to write:

$$\exp(-iEt+ipx) \exp(iEt-ipx) = 1 \quad ((4))$$

The value 1 means that the particle may interact at any time or space point with equal probability. This is different from the equation $x=vt$ which suggests that the center-of-mass has equal probability to exist at each x and t point. It just happens in this case that the value of the probabilities are the same. To consider a case where they are not the same, one may examine a bound state with a wavefunction

$$W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx) \quad ((5))$$

$W^*(x)W(x)$ is a profile for interaction hits. If $W(x)=0$, there is little or no probability, on average, for hits at this x . This is based on the fact that the average uses $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ (and so one does not consider classical motion in time). A particle can still be found at $W(x)=0$ because average kinetic energy is nonzero at such a point. Average classical kinetic energy is the classical average representation of the bound system, but $W(x)W(x)$ shows an interaction-resolution pattern which is also physical. We suggest that quantum mechanics is a combination of both the classical view and the resolution in $x-t$ (\hbar/p , \hbar/E) viewpoints.

For example

$$KE_{ave}(x) + V(x) = E \quad ((6))$$

is a classical equation of conservation of energy. A particle, however, interacts with a potential and one does not consider kinetic energy ($pp/2m$ which is classical) at the center-of-mass point, but rather at the interaction point. The interaction point is treated probabilistically using $\exp(ipx)$. Thus:

$$KE_{ave}(x) = \{ \text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \ pp/2m \ \exp(ipx) \} / W(x) \quad ((7))$$

Writing a $v_{rms}(x)$ is an average quantity, but so is $W(x)W(x)$. Given that $W(x)W(x)$ is a spatial interaction profile and does not represent physical density, we caution against considering a continuity equation as having a classical interpretation.

Continuity Equation

In the literature (1), one often sees a continuity equation:

$$d/dt \text{ partial density}(x,t) = \text{grad dot} (\text{density}(x,t) \ v(x,t)) \quad ((8))$$

where $v(x,t)$ is a velocity field. This approach, however, is applied to a nonrelativistic scenario and the Schrodinger equation and not to the relativistic Klein-Gordon case even though $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ holds for both (although $E = m\sqrt{c^2(1-v^2/c^2)}$ in the relativistic case).

The continuity equation ((8)) seems to arise because it mimics the classical equation:

$$\text{Kinetic energy} = p^2/2m \quad ((9))$$

If kinetic energy is associated with a time derivative (partial) and p , with d/dx partial. The classical action is

$$-Et+px \quad ((10))$$

In both the relativistic and nonrelativistic cases and so in the nonrelativistic case

$$d\text{Action}/dt \text{ partial} = -E \quad \text{and} \quad d\text{Action}/dx = p \quad ((11))$$

There is a classical scheme which allows one to use ((9)) and ((11)) to write

$$d\text{Action}/dt = -1/2m \text{ partial}^2/dx^2 \text{ (Action)} \quad ((12))$$

((12)) has the form of a continuity equation if one absorbs the $-1/2m$, but Action instead of density is used, so this is not the usual physical continuity equation. Thus, we caution on taking the math form ((8)) too seriously, i.e. immediately assigning hydrodynamic motion.

We further note that quantum mechanics is based on $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ and that

$$id/dt \text{ partial} \exp(-iEt) = E \exp(-iEt) \quad \text{and} \quad -id/dx \exp(ipx) = p \exp(ipx) \quad ((13))$$

The derivatives describe the change in phase, not in motion. Hydrodynamic motion is about physical motion in space, not phases.

As a result, for a free particle

$$W(x)W(x) = 1 \quad \text{and} \quad (\text{from (1)}) \quad \text{density}(x,t)v(x,t) = \text{Im} (W^* (-id/dx) W) = 0 \quad ((14))$$

A free particle has no hydrodynamical representation. Even a single particle bound state with $W(x)$ real has no hydrodynamic representation as $W^*(x,t)W(x,t)$ does not change in time. This quantity, however, is not physical density, but an interaction profile in space. We argue, however, that there is a net flow in time and space physically, because a bound particle moves first to the right and then to the left. The statistical quantum calculation, however, considers $a(p)\exp(ipx) + a(-p)\exp(-ipx)$ and so if $a(p)=a(-p)$ then one has $2a(p)\cos(px)$ which shows no net direction. Even in this case, $W(x)W(x)$ is an interaction profile and not a density. As a result, the hydrodynamical model view seems unusual when applied to a single particle bound state.

One may also consider a superposition of bound states with different energies. Each state has no average current flow (although physically there is flow). $W(x,t)$ is a probability. It is the sum

(OR situation of a set of probabilities) and so any flow scenario is an average one based on probability, not on actual physical flow.

$$W(x,t) = \sum_j a(E_j) \exp(-iE_j t) W_j(x) \quad ((15))$$

$$W^*(x,t)W(x,t) = \sum_j W_j(x)W_j(x) + 2 \sum_{k,j (k \neq j)} a(E_j)a(E_k) \cos((E_j-E_k) t) W_j W_k \quad ((16))$$

Here, d/dt partial $W^*(x,t)W(x,t)$ is not 0, so the interaction pattern may change in time (for an ensemble average). Physically, a particle is in a specific j state and there is no change in time. It is only by considering different j states from different ensemble members that one has the average sense of density change in time. The same should then hold for the divergence of the flow. This is again an ensemble effect, while the physical effect of a particle moving back and forth in a single j state is suppressed by the use of $a(p)\exp(ipx)+a(-p)\exp(-ipx)$. As a result, we argue that one must consider a hydrodynamical view with caution.

Conclusion

In conclusion, many papers in the literature (1) consider nonrelativistic quantum mechanics in terms of a continuity equation d/dt partial density(x,t) = grad dot (density * velocity field). Here density = $W^*(x,t)W(x,t)$ and density*velocity field = $\text{Im}(W^* (-id/dx W))$ according to (1). We argue, however, that $W^*(x,t)W(x,t)$ is an interaction profile not a physical density. If one has an ensemble, and does measurements via interactions, then $W(x)=0$ points do not yield measurements (because $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ are averaged together). This does not mean that particles cannot exist at $W(x)=0$ points. $KE_{\text{ave}}(x)$, which is another average, exists at such points. Thus, it is difficult to consider $W^*(x,t)W(x,t)$ as a physical density and to take a classical hydrodynamical description without caution. For a single particle bound state, there is motion to the right and left, but due to averaging of $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$, $W(x)$ is real and (1)'s definition of flux is 0. We show, however, that if one makes a superposition of different energy eigenstates, one has a current flux, even though the $\exp(ipx)$, $\exp(-ipx)$ average suppresses it for any individual state. We thus argue that this is an ensemble flux and not necessarily a physical one.

References

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